

SAMPLING OF VEGETABLES FOR HUMAN CONSUMPTION AND THEIR PROCESSING FOR THE MOLECULAR IDENTIFICATION OF ECHINOCOCCUS SPP. AND TAENIA SPP. EGGS

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1. SCOPE

This Standard Operating Procedure provides instructions for the collection of fresh lettuce and its processing using a sequential sieving for the molecular identification of *Echinococcus* spp. and *Taenia* spp. eggs in the framework of MEME project, One Health European Joint Programme.

2. INTRODUCTION

Cystic and alveolar echinococcosis (CE and AE) are zoonoses involving canids as definitive hosts and a broad spectrum of ungulate species or rodents as intermediate hosts. Humans are considered dead-end hosts for the larval stage of these parasites. AE and CE are important diseases of human interest with a global distribution (Thompson, Deplazes, Lymbery, 2017) caused by infection with *Echinococcus multilocularis* (Em) and *Echinococcus granulosus sensu lato* (Eg), respectively. The infected definitive hosts (mainly red fox for Em and dog for Eg) are shedding eggs in the environment by faeces. The oral ingestion of these eggs may result in human infections. Source attribution for human infections is generally unknown, but hand-to-mouth and the food-waterborne borne transmissions may have a pivotal role. As eggs are inactivated by heat (i.e. cooking), the consumption of fresh vegetables contaminated with viable eggs could lead to human infections.

Very scanty data are currently available on the degree of such contaminations (Tamarozzi et al., 2020). Development of a robust and reliable methods coupling with the concentration of the eggs and sensitive / specific molecular tools for species identification are required to estimate the contamination of fresh vegetables by these parasites. The sequential sieving method recently developed by Guggisberg et al. (2020) will be used with lettuce collected from vegetable markets and kitchen gardens.

3. REFERENCES

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4. SAMPLING

The lettuce sampled should be originated from known *E. multilocularis* and/or *E. granulosus sensu lato* endemic areas, ideally where high prevalence in animal hosts are reported. Only lettuce originated from known geographical areas need to be included. Additionally, sampling should be conducted in private kitchen garden, vegetable market or in a lesser extent supermarkets, where lettuce was cultivated in open land potentially accessible to canids (excluding closed greenhouse cultivation). Lettuce collected from the same field of cultivation will be pooled during the analysis at the rate of two lettuces for private kitchen gardens and four lettuces for commercial producer considering the larger surface of cultivation used. One lettuce sample consists of around 300 g of leaves or the complete lettuce if the total weight is inferior to 300 g.

5. EQUIPMENT

- 5.1. Two small plastic bottles cut in half with lids perforated;
- 5.2. One big plastic bottle cut in half with lid perforated;
- 5.3. One base to support the three bottles funnel;
- 5.4. Nylon filters of different mesh size (21 µm, 40 µm and 105 µm);
- 5.5. Three Single-use plastic pipettes;
- 5.6. One plastic sample bag;
- 5.7. Scissors;
- 5.8. One 50 mL Falcon tubes;
- 5.9. One 2 mL microtube;
- 5.10. Centrifuge;
- 5.11. One clamp;
- 5.12. Analytical balance.

6. REAGENTS

- 6.1. Solution of 0.2% Tween 20.

7. PROCEDURE

Starting material consists of lettuce freshly collected or conserved at +4°C for no more than 3 days. All steps are performed at room temperature as follows:

7.1. Preparation of the equipment and of the samples

- Put the three filters on the perforated lids and screw it on the funnel bottles (starting from the top: 105 μm , 40 μm and 21 μm);
- Annotate the funnel bottles with the size of the filter mesh;
- Place the funnel bottles on the base with the 105 μm mesh filter on the highest place, then the 40 μm and finally the 20 μm mesh filter;
- Place the bottom parts of the big bottle for the collection of the flow-through;
- Put 300 g of lettuce leaves, giving priority to those outer leaves whose appearance would not require removal from the consumer, in a sample plastic bag;
- Add 500 mL of 0.2% Tween 20 in the sample plastic bag;
- Close the bag and shake it vigorously for more than 30 sec while stirring to detach as much residue as possible from the leaves.

7.2. Sequential sieving

- Using a pair of scissors, cut an angle at the bottom of the bag to create an opening for pouring the contents to be filtered;
- Pour the solution into the upper bottle (105 μm mesh size) and let it will flow through the following bottles;
- Squeeze the bag well so that the maximum amount of solution is recovered;
- Remove the lettuce and then, using a pipette containing 0.02% Tween 20 to rinse the bag, then filter the rinsing liquid;
- Use a single-use pipette in each of the bottle to facilitate the flow;
- Once the solution has been fully filtered, starting from the top use the single-use pipette to rinse the bottles with the 0.2% Tween 20 solution.

7.3. Collection of the substrate from the 20 µm filter

- a) Unscrew the lid and use clamp to retrieve the 20 µm filter;
- b) Hold the filter with the forceps in the 50 mL Falcon tube and use the 0.2% Tween 20 pipette to rinse the filter;
- c) Centrifuge the 50 mL Falcon tube for 5 min at 1000 g;
- d) Discard the supernatant;
- e) Collect the pellet in a 2 mL microtube and store at +4°C until the DNA extraction.

7.4. Detection by molecular biology

DNA extraction is realized using Blood & Tissue kit (Qiagen) with an additional overnight lysis step. The detection of *E. multilocularis* is performed by a real-time PCR assay as previously described (Knapp et al., 2016) when classical PCR followed by sequencing is used to identify *Taenia* sp. (Trachsel et al., 2007).

8. SAFETY MEASURES

The operator should wear individual protection devices during the test performance. For general safety measures, refer to the guidelines of CDC (http://www.who.int/ihr/publications/bioriskmanagement_1/en/).